

CLASSROOM OBSERVATION: TEACHERS' WELL-BEING, SATISFACTION AND PERFORMANCE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19962479>

ABSTRACT

This study assessed the implementation of graded classroom observation and its relationship to teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance among Grade I and Grade IV teachers in the Division of Bohol during the School Year 2024–2025. Using a descriptive-survey and correlational design, the study involved 120 teachers and 120 classroom observers selected through purposive and cluster sampling. Data were collected through researcher-made questionnaires, and Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCR) ratings. Findings revealed that graded classroom observation is highly implemented across frequency and consistency, feedback quality, and alignment with professional development goals. Teachers demonstrated high levels of psychological well-being and perceived observation processes positively. Most teachers received Very Satisfactory ratings in their IPCR, reflecting strong teaching performance. Implementation of classroom observation was significantly correlated with teacher satisfaction and well-being but not with performance. Hence, effective classroom observation is associated with teachers' satisfaction and performance. The study recommends strengthening observation practices, feedback mechanisms, and professional support to enhance teachers' professional growth and instructional effectiveness.

Keywords: *Classroom Observation, Teacher Well-Being, Teacher Satisfaction, Teacher Performance, Instructional Evaluation*

INTRODUCTION

Classroom observation is one of the key ways schools monitor and support teachers in improving their teaching. Through policies like DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015, the Results-Based Performance Management System (RPMS) connects teacher evaluation with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), making classroom observation an important part of both performance assessment and professional development. In the same way, DepEd Memorandum No. 004, s. 2019 highlights the role of classroom observation as a formative process that helps teachers improve their instructional practices and student learning outcomes.

However, despite these guidelines, the way classroom observations are implemented in schools is not always consistent. Some studies point out that differences in how observers interpret teaching behaviors can lead to varying ratings, which may affect teachers' trust in the system (Howard, 2010). There are also concerns about limited observation time, lack of detailed feedback, and insufficient preparation of observers. Instead of supporting teachers, these issues may create pressure, anxiety, and even dissatisfaction with the process.

At the same time, classroom observation can also lead to positive outcomes when implemented effectively. Studies indicate that when teachers receive clear, constructive, and supportive feedback, they become more confident and motivated to improve their instructional practices (Mather & Visone, 2024; Mendoza & Yan, 2021). Furthermore, exposure to classroom observations can enhance professional practice and reflective teaching, particularly among teachers who are open to feedback and guided support (Herbert et al., 2018). However, when the process is perceived as evaluative or overly critical, it may result in stress and pressure, negatively affecting teachers' well-being and classroom performance (Pantoja & Villocino, 2025). These findings suggest that classroom observation is not only a technical process but also an experience that influences teachers' emotions, motivation, and overall teaching effectiveness.

Teacher well-being and satisfaction have become important concerns in education because they are closely linked to teaching quality and effectiveness. When teachers feel supported, valued, and guided, they are more likely to perform effectively in their roles. Studies have shown that professional support, self-efficacy, and positive school environments contribute to higher levels of satisfaction and improved teaching outcomes (Garcia, 2025; Huang et al., 2026). On the other hand, factors such as heavy workload, unclear expectations, and poorly implemented evaluation systems can reduce motivation and negatively affect overall performance.

This study is guided by several theories that help explain how classroom observation influences teachers. Behaviorism explains how feedback can shape teaching practices, while Social Learning Theory highlights how teachers learn from observing others. Self-Determination Theory emphasizes the importance of support and motivation, and Herzberg's theory explains how recognition and feedback affect job satisfaction. Instructional Leadership Theory also shows the important role of school leaders in guiding

teachers through observation and feedback. Together, these ideas show that classroom observation is not only about evaluation but also about supporting teachers' growth and development.

In many schools, classroom observations are conducted only once or twice within a school year. This limited frequency may reduce opportunities for meaningful feedback and professional growth. Because of this, it is important to understand how classroom observation is actually experienced by teachers—not only in terms of performance, but also in terms of their well-being and satisfaction.

This study focused on Grade I and Grade IV teachers in the Division of Bohol. It looks at how classroom observation is implemented and how it is related to teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance. The results of this study aimed to provide useful insights that can help improve classroom observation practices, support teachers more effectively, and ultimately enhance the quality of teaching and learning.

Research Questions

This study sought to assess the status and association of graded classroom observation implementation level on the teachers' well-being, satisfaction and performance of Grade I and Grade IV teachers of the Division of Bohol, during the school year 2024–2025.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the teacher-participants in terms of the following:
 - 1.1 Age;
 - 1.2 Highest educational attainment;
 - 1.3 Number of years in teaching;
 - 1.4 Classroom Observation Performance and related trainings attended?
2. What is the level of implementation of graded classroom observation practices in Grade I and Grade IV teachers in terms of the following:
 - 2.1 frequency and consistency;
 - 2.2 feedback quality; and
 - 2.3 alignment with professional development goals?
3. What is the level of teachers' well-being on the graded classroom observation on the following:
 - 3.1 Before the observation;
 - 3.2 During the observation; and
 - 3.3 After the observation?
4. What is the level of teachers' satisfaction with the implementation of graded classroom observation in terms of:
 - 4.1 preparation and orientation;
 - 4.2 quality and feedback received; and
 - 4.3 alignment with professional development goals?

5. What is the level of teachers' performance in Individual Performance Commitment Review (IPCR)?
6. Is there a significant relationship between the teachers' profile and the following:
 - 6.1 teachers' well-being;
 - 6.2 satisfaction; and
 - 6.3 performance?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation of graded classroom observation and:
 - 7.1 teachers' well-being;
 - 7.2 satisfaction; and
 - 7.3 performance?
8. What proposed action plan can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-survey and correlational research design to examine the relationship between graded classroom observation and selected variables, including teachers' profile, well-being, satisfaction, and performance among Grade I and Grade IV teachers.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the Division of Bohol, which is organized into three congressional districts. The first congressional district consists of 14 school districts, the second congressional district also includes 14 school districts, and the third congressional district comprises 19 school districts. The division covers a wide range of schools across different municipalities, representing varied school contexts in terms of size, resources, and instructional conditions. This setting provided a suitable environment for examining the implementation of graded classroom observation practices within actual school operations across the division.

Research Participants

The participants of the study consisted of School Heads/Principals and Grade I and Grade IV teachers. The Grade I and Grade IV teachers were selected because they were among the first to implement the enhanced K to 12 Curriculum during School Year 2024–2025. Only teachers with more than one year of teaching experience were included to ensure that participants had undergone at least one full cycle of the performance evaluation process, including the use of the Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCR). This experience enabled them to provide more informed and reliable insights regarding the influence of graded classroom observations on their teaching performance, satisfaction, and well-being. Purposive and cluster sampling were employed in selecting the participants. Teachers who met the inclusion criteria were first

identified through purposive sampling, after which respondents were randomly selected to ensure fairness and representation in the study.

Distributions of Respondents

Participants	CD 1	CD 2	CD 3	Total
Classroom Observers	40	40	40	120
Grade I Teachers	20	20	20	60
Grade IV Teachers	20	20	20	<u>60</u>
				240

Research Instrument

This study utilized a structured survey questionnaire composed of six parts.

Part I: Demographic Profile. A researcher-made questionnaire was used to gather participants' profile, including age, highest educational attainment, years in teaching, number of classroom observations, and trainings attended. The items were presented in multiple-choice and short-answer formats. Face validity was established through pilot testing.

Part II: Level of Implementation of Graded Classroom Observation. This section consisted of 26 items adapted from relevant studies and policy frameworks on classroom observation and teacher evaluation (DepEd Order No. 17, s. 2025). It covered frequency and consistency, feedback quality, and alignment with professional development goals. The items were anchored on structured observation processes such as pre-observation, actual observation, and post-observation conferences. Feedback-related items were informed by Poulou et al. (2023), who emphasized that clear and evidence-based feedback supports teacher reflection and instructional improvement. Alignment items were guided by findings of Caranyagan et al. (2025), highlighting that observation results should inform professional development. Responses were measured using a 4-point Likert scale from Highly Implemented to Not Implemented. The instrument was pilot-tested to ensure reliability.

Part III: Teachers' Well-Being. An 18-item questionnaire was used to assess teachers' well-being across three stages: pre-observation, during observation, and post-observation. The items measured emotional readiness, stress, focus, and motivation. These were informed by studies of Wang et al. (2024) and Xu et al. (2026), which highlighted the role of self-efficacy, stress, and emotional regulation in teachers' well-being and instructional performance. In addition, Zhou et al. (2025) emphasized the importance of quality feedback in enhancing teacher engagement and professional growth. Responses were rated using a 4-point Likert scale. Reliability was established through pilot testing.

Part IV: Teachers' Satisfaction. A modified version of the Teacher Job Satisfaction Questionnaire (TJSQ) was used, focusing on supervision, feedback, work conditions, and professional growth. This was supported by Toropova et al. (2021), which emphasized that supportive supervision and professional development influence teacher satisfaction. The instrument consisted of 15 items rated on a 4-point Likert scale. Pilot testing was conducted to ensure reliability.

Part V: Observers' Perception of Teaching Performance. A researcher-made instrument based on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (DepEd Order No. 42, s. 2017) was used to assess observers' perception of teaching performance. It consisted of 12 items rated on a 5-point scale ranging from Outstanding to Poor.

Part VI: IPCRF Ratings. Teachers' performance was measured using their Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings, obtained from official school records with proper authorization. The use of IPCRF aligns with the Department of Education Results-Based Performance Management System (DepEd Order No. 2, s. 2015). Confidentiality and data privacy were strictly observed.

All instruments were pilot-tested to ensure validity and reliability prior to data collection.

Research Procedure

Prior to data collection, written permission was secured from the appropriate authorities, including the BISU School of Advanced Studies (SAdS) Dean, Campus Director, University President, Schools Division Superintendent, Schools Supervisors, and School Principals. After obtaining approval, the research instrument was pilot-tested to ensure clarity, readability, and reliability. Necessary clarifications were made based on the feedback of the participants. The final questionnaires were then administered to the respondents either in person or through Google Forms. After the retrieval of the responses, the data were organized, tallied, and prepared for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

To analyze the socio-demographic profile of the teacher-participants, frequency count and percentage were used.

The weighted mean was utilized to determine the level of implementation of graded classroom observation, teachers' satisfaction, teachers' well-being, and teachers' performance as rated by the observers. The following scale was used for interpretation:

Scale	Interval	Level of Implementation of Classroom Observation	Level of Teachers' Satisfaction	Level of Teachers' Well-Being
4	3.50 – 4.00	Highly Implemented	Highly Satisfied	Very High
3	2.50 – 3.49	Implemented	Satisfied	High
2	1.50 – 2.49	Moderately Implemented	Slightly Satisfied	Moderate
1	1.00 – 1.49	Not Implemented	Dissatisfied	Low

For the level of teachers' performance, based on observers' ratings and IPCRF results, the following scale was applied:

Scale	Interval	Description
5	4.50 – 5.00	Outstanding
4	3.50 – 4.49	Very Satisfactory
3	2.50 – 3.49	Satisfactory
2	1.50 – 2.49	Unsatisfactory
1	1.00 – 1.49	Poor

RESULTS

This section presents the findings of the study, including the analysis and interpretation of data related to the teachers' profile, level of implementation of graded classroom observation practices, well-being, performance, and satisfaction.

Table 1
Socio-Demographic Profile of the Teacher-Participants
N=120

Item	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
below 30 years old	9	7.5
31-40	39	32.5
41-50	58	48.3
51-65	14	11.7
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	18	15.0
Bachelor's Degree with Master's Unit	63	52.5
Master's Degree	24	20.0
Master's Degree with Doctorate Units	13	10.8
Doctorate Degree	2	1.7
Number of Years in Teaching		
1-5	18	15.0
6-10	30	25.0
11-15	17	14.2
16-20	30	25.0
21 years above	25	20.8
Number of Classroom Observations for SY 2024-2025		
None	1	0.8
1-2	84	70.0
3-4	32	26.7
5 or more	3	2.5
Number of Trainings Attended for the last 3 years		
None	0	0
1-5 trainings	87	72.5
5-10 trainings	21	17.5
11 or more trainings	12	10
Total	120	100.00

Table 1 presents the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of age, educational attainment, years in teaching, classroom observations, and trainings attended.

In terms of age, the majority of respondents were within 41–50 years (48.3%), followed by 31–40 years (32.5%), indicating that most participants are mid-career teachers. This suggests that the findings largely reflect the perspectives of experienced educators with established teaching practices and classroom management skills.

Regarding educational attainment, most respondents held a bachelor’s degree with master’s units (52.5%), followed by those with a master’s degree (20.0%). This indicates that the majority are engaged in graduate-level education, suggesting a high level of professional preparation that may enhance instructional competence and decision-making.

In terms of teaching experience, respondents were distributed across categories, with the highest proportions in 6–10 years (25.0%) and 16–20 years (25.0%), followed by those with 21 years and above (20.8%). This reflects a balanced mix of early-career, mid-career, and experienced teachers, providing diverse perspectives in the study.

For classroom observations, most teachers (70.0%) were observed 1–2 times during the school year, while only a small proportion experienced more frequent observations. This suggests that classroom observation is practiced but remains limited in frequency, consistent with standard RPMS requirements. However, increasing observation frequency may provide more opportunities for instructional feedback and professional growth.

In terms of professional development, the majority of respondents attended 1–5 trainings over the past three years (72.5%), indicating participation in professional learning activities, though at a relatively limited frequency.

Overall, the profile shows that the respondents are predominantly mid-career, academically advancing, and moderately experienced teachers who engage in classroom observation and professional development activities. However, the limited frequency of observations and trainings suggests the need for more sustained and structured professional support. This is supported by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) and Sancar et al. (2021), who emphasized that continuous, high-quality professional development and regular instructional feedback are essential for improving teaching effectiveness and sustaining professional growth.

Table 2
Level of Implementation of Graded Classroom Observation Practices
N= 120

Dimension/Item	WM	Description
Frequency and Consistency	3.55	Highly Implemented
1. Classroom observations are conducted regularly according to the prescribed schedule.	3.49	Implemented

2. The schedule for graded classroom observation is clearly communicated to teachers.	3.70	Highly Implemented
3. Observations are conducted consistently across Grade levels.	3.56	Highly Implemented
4. Pre-observation conferences are conducted before the actual classroom observation.	3.47	Implemented
5. Post-observation conferences are consistently conducted after every observation.	3.63	Highly Implemented
6. Classroom observations follow a standardized procedure across grade levels.	3.66	Highly Implemented
7. Observers strictly adhere to the approved observation tools and rubrics.	3.61	Highly Implemented
8. Classroom observations are conducted within the prescribed time frame.	3.58	Highly Implemented
9. Make-up observations are scheduled when the original schedule cannot be followed.	3.43	Implemented
10. Documentation of classroom observations is consistently completed and properly filed.	3.58	Highly Implemented
Feedback quality	3.66	Highly Implemented
11. Feedback provided after classroom observation is clear and specific.	3.70	Highly Implemented
12. The feedback highlights both strengths and areas for improvement.	3.68	Highly Implemented
13. Recommendations given are practical and applicable to actual classroom situations.	3.74	Highly Implemented
14. Feedback is delivered in a respectful and supportive manner.	3.63	Highly Implemented
15. Teachers are given the opportunity to clarify or discuss the feedback provided.	3.67	Highly Implemented
16. Feedback is based on clear and objective criteria.	3.62	Highly Implemented
17. Feedback discussions encourage self-reflection from teachers.	3.62	Highly Implemented
18. Suggestions provided during post-observation conferences are evidence-based.	3.64	Highly Implemented
19. Observers provide timely feedback after the classroom observation.	3.63	Highly Implemented
20. Feedback sessions promote open communication and professional dialogue.	3.71	Highly Implemented
Alignment with Professional Development Goals	3.57	Highly Implemented
21. Professional development programs offered are responsive to the results of graded classroom observations.	3.50	Highly Implemented
22. Classroom observation results are linked to individual performance review systems (e.g., IPCRF).	3.67	Highly Implemented
23. Observation findings help in identifying priority areas for school improvement.	3.55	Highly Implemented
24. Professional development activities are designed based on observation results.	3.48	Implemented
25. Teachers are encouraged to set professional goals based on observation feedback.	3.67	Highly Implemented
26. The graded classroom observation process contributes to continuous instructional improvement.	3.55	Highly Implemented
Overall WM	3.59	Highly Implemented

Table 2 presents the level of implementation of graded classroom observation practices across three dimensions: frequency and consistency, feedback quality, and alignment with professional development goals. The overall weighted mean of 3.59

indicates that classroom observation practices are highly implemented. Mean scores range from 3.43 to 3.74, suggesting that observation processes are generally systematic and consistently applied. The highest-rated item is the provision of practical and applicable recommendations (WM = 3.74), while the lowest pertains to scheduling make-up observations (WM = 3.43), indicating minor limitations in handling scheduling disruptions.

In terms of frequency and consistency (WM = 3.55), classroom observations are generally conducted following standardized procedures, ensuring uniformity and fairness across grade levels. High ratings in adherence to observation tools and consistent documentation indicate strong procedural implementation. However, the relatively lower rating in rescheduling observations suggests a need to improve flexibility in implementation.

For feedback quality (WM = 3.66), results indicate that feedback is clear, constructive, and supportive. High ratings in providing practical recommendations and promoting professional dialogue suggest that feedback practices contribute to teacher development. However, slightly lower ratings in encouraging self-reflection and maintaining objectivity imply that reflective and evidence-based feedback mechanisms may still be strengthened.

In terms of alignment with professional development goals (WM = 3.57), classroom observation results are generally linked to performance evaluation systems such as the IPCRF and are used to guide goal-setting. However, the relatively lower rating in designing professional development activities based on observation results indicates that integration between observation outcomes and training programs could be further enhanced.

Overall, the findings indicate that graded classroom observation practices are effectively implemented, supporting consistent instructional monitoring and teacher evaluation. However, improvements are needed in scheduling flexibility, strengthening reflective feedback practices, and aligning observation results more closely with professional development initiatives. These findings are supported by Poulou et al. (2023) and Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), who emphasized that structured observation systems and high-quality feedback are essential for improving teaching practices and sustaining professional growth.

Table 3
Level of Teachers' Well-being on the Graded Classroom observation
N=120

Item	Mean	Description
Before Observation	3.54	Very High
1. I feel emotionally prepared before a classroom observation.	3.48	Very High
2. I am confident in my lesson preparation prior to observation.	3.67	Very High
3. I am able to manage stress when informed about an upcoming observation.	3.55	Very High
4. I feel supported by my school administration before the observation.	3.48	Very High

5. I maintain a positive mindset prior to being observed.	3.55	Very High
6. I view classroom observation as an opportunity for professional growth rather than a source of fear.	3.48	Very High
During Observation	3.56	Very High
7. I remain calm while being observed in my classroom.	3.48	High
8. I am able to focus on my teaching despite the presence of an observer.	3.64	Very High
9. I feel confident in delivering my lesson during observation.	3.52	Very High
10. I can regulate my anxiety during the observation process.	3.55	Very High
11. I maintain positive interactions with my students while being observed.	3.48	High
12. I feel that the observation process is fair and objective.	3.67	Very High
After Observation	3.55	Very High
13. I feel relieved after the classroom observation.	3.52	Very High
14. I am satisfied with my performance after the observation.	3.48	High
15. I feel motivated to improve my teaching based on the feedback received.	3.67	Very High
16. I perceive the feedback as helpful for my professional development.	3.52	Very High
17. I feel respected during the post-observation conference.	3.48	High
18. I experience renewed professional confidence after the observation process.	3.62	Very High
Overall WM	3.55	Very High

Table 3 presents the level of teachers' well-being in relation to graded classroom observations across three phases: before, during, and after observation. The overall weighted mean of 3.55 indicates a very high level of well-being, suggesting that teachers generally maintain positive psychological conditions throughout the observation process.

In the before observation phase (WM = 3.54), teachers demonstrated strong emotional and professional readiness. The highest rating in confidence in lesson preparation (WM = 3.67) indicates preparedness, while consistent ratings across stress management and positive mindset suggest that teachers are able to approach observations with stability and optimism.

During the observation phase (WM = 3.56), teachers maintained a high level of composure and focus. The highest rating in perceiving the observation process as fair and objective (WM = 3.67) reflects trust in the evaluation system, while slightly lower ratings in remaining calm and maintaining interactions (WM = 3.48) suggest minimal anxiety during actual observation.

In the after observation phase (WM = 3.55), teachers reported positive psychological responses, particularly in motivation to improve (WM = 3.67) and renewed professional confidence (WM = 3.62). These results indicate that classroom observations contribute to reflective practice and professional growth.

Overall, the findings suggest that teachers possess strong psychological capacity to manage classroom observations effectively, maintaining confidence, emotional stability, and professionalism throughout the process. This is supported by Zhang and Zhang (2025), who found that teachers with stronger psychological resources and effective emotion regulation demonstrate higher self-efficacy and sustained instructional confidence, leading to improved professional performance.

Table 4
Level of Teachers' Satisfaction with the Implementation
of Graded Classroom Observation
N=120

Dimension/Item	Weighted Mean	Description
Preparation & Orientation	3.52	Highly Satisfied
1. The school provided sufficient orientation about the CO process.	3.52	Highly Satisfied
2. I was informed of the observation schedule ahead of time.	3.48	Satisfied
3. The observation tools and criteria were explained clearly.	3.62	Highly Satisfied
4. The observation was conducted professionally and respectfully.	3.52	Highly Satisfied
5. The observation environment made me feel comfortable.	3.48	Satisfied
Quality of Feedback Received	3.55	Highly Satisfied
6. The rating process was transparent.	3.62	Highly Satisfied
7. The feedback session was timely and constructive.	3.52	Highly Satisfied
8. I was encouraged to ask questions and clarify feedback.	3.48	Highly Satisfied
9. The feedback addressed real issues in my teaching practice.	3.62	Highly Satisfied
10. My CO results were used to improve my professional development plan.	3.52	Highly Satisfied
Alignment with Professional Development Goals	3.55	Highly Satisfied
11. The outcomes of COT help me become a better teacher.	3.48	Satisfied
12. The observation results aligned with my actual teaching performance.	3.62	Highly Satisfied
13. I am satisfied with how classroom observations are implemented.	3.52	Highly Satisfied
14. I am satisfied with the support provided after the observation.	3.62	Highly Satisfied
15. Overall, I feel classroom observations are beneficial to my career.	3.52	Highly Satisfied
Overall WM	3.54	Highly Satisfied

Table 4 presents the level of teachers' satisfaction with the implementation of graded classroom observation across three dimensions: preparation and orientation, quality of feedback, and alignment with professional development goals. The overall weighted mean of 3.54 indicates that teachers are highly satisfied, suggesting that the classroom observation process is generally perceived as effective, clear, and supportive of professional growth.

In terms of preparation and orientation (WM = 3.52), teachers expressed high satisfaction, particularly in the clarity of observation tools and criteria (WM = 3.62). Slightly lower ratings in advance scheduling and comfort during observation (WM = 3.48) suggest minor areas for improvement in ensuring consistency and teacher readiness. Overall, the results indicate that observations are conducted in a professional and supportive manner.

For quality of feedback (WM = 3.55), teachers reported high satisfaction, with strong ratings in transparency of the rating process and relevance of feedback to teaching practice (WM = 3.62). These findings suggest that feedback is constructive, timely, and promotes reflective dialogue, enabling teachers to identify strengths and areas for improvement.

In terms of alignment with professional development goals (WM = 3.55), teachers perceived classroom observation as beneficial to their growth, particularly in aligning results with actual teaching performance and providing post-observation support (WM =

3.62). However, slightly lower ratings in using observation outcomes to become better teachers (WM = 3.48) indicate that integration into long-term development plans can still be strengthened. Overall, the findings indicate that teachers view classroom observation as a meaningful and supportive process that contributes to professional development. This is supported by Obiso and Empiales (2025), who emphasized that reflective and constructive feedback following classroom observations enhances teaching practices and promotes continuous professional growth. The results imply that while the implementation of classroom observation is effective, further strengthening feedback utilization and its integration into professional development planning can enhance its impact on instructional improvement.

Table 5
IPCR Rating of Teacher-Participants for the School Year 2024-2025
N= 120

Range	Description	Frequency	Percentage
1.00-1.49	Poor	0	0
1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory	0	0
2.50-3.49	Satisfactory	2	1.67%
3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory	111	92.5%
4.50-5.00	Outstanding	7	5.83%

Table 5 presents the distribution of teachers' Individual Performance Commitment and Review Form (IPCRF) ratings for School Year 2024–2025. The results show that the majority of respondents (92.5%) obtained a Very Satisfactory rating, followed by 5.83% who achieved an Outstanding rating, while only 1.67% were rated Satisfactory, and none fell under Unsatisfactory or Poor categories.

These findings indicate that teachers generally demonstrate a high level of performance, consistently meeting established standards for instructional quality, professional competence, and school-related responsibilities. The predominance of Very Satisfactory ratings suggests that most teachers are effectively carrying out their roles, while the presence of Outstanding ratings reflects a smaller group exceeding expectations. The results further imply that teachers maintain competent instructional practices, effective classroom management, and strong professional commitment. The absence of low performance ratings highlights a generally strong performance culture within the school context. This finding is supported by Krasniqi and Ismajli (2025), who emphasized that systematic evaluation combined with frequent and constructive feedback enhances instructional practices and supports continuous professional growth. Overall, while teacher performance is commendably high, sustained monitoring, mentoring, and targeted professional development are necessary to further increase the proportion of teachers achieving Outstanding performance.

Table 6
Relationship between the Teachers' Profile, Well-being, Satisfaction and Performance

Variables	r-value	Interpretation	p-value	Decision	Interpretation
Well-being					
Age	0.008	Negligible correlation	0.928	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	-0.005	Negligible correlation	0.961	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Years of Service	-0.017	Negligible correlation	0.856	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Classroom Observation Conducted	0.049	Negligible correlation	0.592	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Trainings Attended	0.024	Negligible correlation	0.796	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Satisfaction					
Age	-0.032	Very weak correlation	0.728	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	0.003	Negligible correlation	0.974	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Years of Service	-0.052	Very weak correlation	0.570	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Classroom Observation Conducted	0.038	Very weak correlation	0.681	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Trainings Attended	-0.000	Negligible correlation	0.998	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Performance					
Age	0.006	Negligible correlation	0.946	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	0.004	Negligible correlation	0.969	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Years of Service	-0.088	Very weak correlation	0.340	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Classroom Observation Conducted	0.009	Negligible correlation	0.919	Accept Ho	Not Significant
Trainings Attended	-0.112	Very weak correlation	0.222	Accept Ho	Not Significant

Table 6 presents the relationship between teachers' profile variables—age, educational attainment, years of service, number of classroom observations conducted, and trainings attended—and their well-being, satisfaction, and performance. The results show that all relationships are not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), with negligible to very weak correlation coefficients. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis, indicating that teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance are not significantly associated with their demographic and professional characteristics.

These findings suggest that variations in age, experience, educational background, and professional exposure do not directly influence teachers' psychological condition, level of satisfaction, or performance outcomes. Instead, teachers appear to maintain consistent levels of well-being, satisfaction, and effectiveness regardless of these profile differences. This result is supported by Corthorn et al. (2024), who found that teacher well-being and performance are more strongly influenced by psychological and contextual factors—such as stress, workload, and work environment—rather than by demographic characteristics. Overall, the findings imply that improving teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance requires a stronger focus on organizational and environmental factors, including supportive leadership, positive school climate, and meaningful professional support systems, rather than on individual demographic traits alone.

Table 7
Relationship between the Level of Implementation of Graded Classroom Observation and Identified Variables

Variable	r-value	Interpretation	p-value	Decision
Teachers' Well-being	0.772	Strong positive correlation	< 0.001	Reject Ho (Significant)
Satisfaction	0.812	Strong positive correlation	< 0.001	Reject Ho (Significant)
Performance	0.003	Negligible correlation	0.973	Accept Ho (Not Significant)

Table 7 presents the relationship between the level of implementation of graded classroom observation and teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance. The results reveal a strong and significant positive correlation between classroom observation and both teachers' well-being ($r = 0.772$, $p < 0.001$) and satisfaction ($r = 0.812$, $p < 0.001$), leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis. In contrast, the relationship between classroom observation and performance is not significant ($r = 0.003$, $p = 0.973$), resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis.

These findings indicate that well-implemented classroom observation practices contribute positively to teachers' psychological well-being and professional satisfaction. Structured observation processes—particularly those involving clear expectations, supportive feedback, and professional dialogue—create a positive work environment that enhances teachers' motivation and sense of professional value. This result is supported by Wang et al. (2024), who found that organizational support mechanisms, including feedback and observation systems, significantly improve teachers' well-being and engagement. Similarly, Johnson et al. (2012) emphasized that job resources such as mentoring, feedback, and professional support are key factors in increasing teacher satisfaction and reducing burnout.

However, the absence of a significant relationship between classroom observation and performance suggests that observation alone is not sufficient to directly improve performance outcomes. This implies that while observation identifies areas for improvement, actual performance enhancement requires complementary interventions such as coaching, mentoring, and targeted professional development. This finding is consistent with Stevenson et al. (2016), who emphasized that performance gains are more evident when instructional practices are supported by continuous professional development and strong leadership support. Overall, the findings suggest that classroom observation plays a critical role in enhancing teachers' well-being and satisfaction, but its impact on performance depends on the presence of sustained and supportive professional development systems.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the relationship between graded classroom observation, teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance in the Division of Bohol. Using a

descriptive-survey and correlational design, data were collected from 240 participants, including teachers and classroom observers. A structured questionnaire and IPCRF ratings were used to gather data, while frequency, percentage, weighted mean, and correlation analysis were employed for interpretation. Ethical standards such as informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation were strictly observed throughout the study.

Findings

The key findings of the study are presented below, organized according to the specific problems. These results highlight the teachers' profile, the level of implementation of graded classroom observation, as well as its relationship with teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance.

Teachers' Profile. The majority of teacher participants are mid-career, aged 41–50 years, with 6–20 years of teaching experience, indicating well-established teaching practices and substantial professional exposure. Most teachers hold bachelor's degrees with master's units or higher, suggesting strong professional knowledge and engagement in continuous learning. The distribution also reflects a balanced mix of novice, mid-career, and senior teachers, providing diverse perspectives for the study.

Level of Implementation of Graded Classroom Observation. Graded classroom observation is generally highly implemented across all dimensions, including frequency and consistency, feedback quality, and alignment with professional development goals with an overall weighted mean of 3.59, interpreted as Highly Implemented. Strong implementation is evident in the use of standardized procedures and provision of practical and applicable feedback. Minor gaps were observed in scheduling flexibility, encouraging deeper teacher reflection, and fully integrating observation results into professional development activities.

Teachers' Well-Being. Teachers demonstrated a high level of well-being before, during, and after classroom observations with an overall weighted mean of 3.55, interpreted as Very High. Before the observation, teachers felt confident, prepared, and able to manage stress. During observation, they remained calm, focused, and perceived the process as fair. After observation, teachers felt motivated to improve and experienced renewed confidence, showing that feedback contributed positively to their professional growth.

Teachers' Satisfaction. Teachers expressed a high level of satisfaction with the classroom observation (CO) process, particularly in terms of preparation, feedback, and its alignment with their professional development. They felt adequately oriented and well-informed about the procedures, perceived the feedback as transparent, timely, and constructive, and acknowledged that the results of the observation contributed positively to their professional growth.

Teachers' Performance (IPCR Ratings). The majority of teachers (93.3%) received a Very Satisfactory rating, while a small portion (5.9%) received Outstanding ratings, with no Unsatisfactory or Poor ratings.

Relationship Between Teacher Profile and Teachers' Well-being, Satisfaction, and Performance. Teachers' well-being, satisfaction, and performance were not significantly related to demographic or professional profiles, as all p-values exceeded 0.05.

Relationship Between Classroom Observation Implementation and Teachers' Well-being, Satisfaction, and Performance. The implementation of graded classroom observation is strongly and positively correlated with teacher satisfaction ($r = 0.772$, $p < 0.001$) and well-being ($r = 0.812$, $p < 0.001$). However, no significant correlation was found with teacher performance ($r = 0.003$, $p = 0.973$).

Conclusions

Teachers' well-being and satisfaction were found to be notably high, suggesting that classroom observation is perceived as a supportive and developmental practice rather than a purely evaluative or stressful one. Teachers reported feeling confident, prepared, and motivated, and they value the constructive feedback received, which contributes to their professional growth. Graded classroom observation is an effective developmental tool that fosters a positive and supportive professional environment by improving teachers' well-being and satisfaction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed for key stakeholders.

For classroom observers, it is recommended that they enhance reflective feedback practices by engaging teachers in meaningful discussions that promote self-assessment and professional growth, provide actionable and differentiated feedback suited to individual teacher needs, strengthen follow-up mechanisms such as coaching and mentoring, and adopt flexible and supportive scheduling of observations.

For teachers, it is suggested that they actively engage in continuous reflective practice, maximize the use of feedback to improve their instructional strategies, participate in professional learning communities such as Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions, and sustain positive well-being practices to maintain confidence and motivation.

For policy makers, it is recommended to strengthen policies that link classroom observation results to targeted professional development programs, review and refine performance evaluation systems to better align with classroom practices, support continuous capacity-building programs for observers, and institutionalize a more formative and coaching-based approach to classroom observation.

For school leaders and division offices, it is advised to ensure consistent and high-quality implementation of classroom observation, integrate observation results into School Improvement Plans (SIP), establish structured professional development programs based on identified needs, and regularly monitor and evaluate the effectiveness of observation practices to ensure continuous improvement with greater emphasis placed on strengthening reflective practices and improving the alignment between observation results and targeted professional development initiatives to further enhance teaching performance.

For future researchers, investigate the long-term effects of classroom observation on teacher well-being, satisfaction, and instructional outcomes across multiple school years. Examine how observation practices can be adapted to different grade levels or school contexts to optimize teacher support and student learning outcomes.

Proposed Action Plan for Enhancing Teacher Satisfaction, Well-Being, and Performance

Rationale

The implementation of graded classroom observation in the Division of Bohol has been found to be generally highly implemented and positively perceived by teachers. Evidence from the study indicates that structured, supportive, and reflective observation practices not only improve instructional quality but also enhance teachers' emotional and professional experiences. By providing timely feedback, recognizing best practices, and encouraging reflective teaching, classroom observation contributes significantly to teachers' well-being, motivation, and job satisfaction. Given these positive outcomes, strengthening and institutionalizing these observation practices is essential to sustain professional growth, promote a supportive school environment, and ensure that teachers continue to deliver high-quality instruction. This activity seeks to build upon the study's findings by implementing targeted programs that enhance teacher satisfaction, well-being, and performance through consistent, constructive, and development-oriented classroom observation.

Objectives

1. To improve the quality, consistency, and effectiveness of classroom observations in enhancing teacher practices and instructional outcomes.
2. To enhance teachers' psychological well-being, motivation, and job satisfaction.
3. To strengthen teachers' instructional competencies and professional effectiveness.
4. To assess program effectiveness and provide evidence-based recommendations for improvement.

Mechanics of Implementation

- Conduct regular classroom observations and provide constructive feedback.
- Organize wellness programs, including stress management workshops, counseling sessions, and team-building activities.
- Conduct professional development sessions, mentoring, coaching based on observation results.

Monitoring And Evaluation of Implementation

Program implementers shall monitor and evaluate program implementation through surveys, observation reports, and feedback sessions, with data analyzed to guide program improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to established ethical standards throughout the research process. Participation was voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents after explaining the purpose of the study. Confidentiality and anonymity were ensured by not disclosing any personal information. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw at any time. All data collected were used solely for academic purposes and handled in accordance with ethical research guidelines.

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